

Original Research

Supplier Orientation and Furniture Manufacturing Small and Medium Enterprises' Performance in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania: Customer Loyalty's Role

Gordian Stanslaus Bwemelo¹
Department of Marketing and Enterprise Management, Moshi Cooperative
University, Moshi, Tanzania

Robert Galan Mashenene
Department of Marketing, College of Business Education, Mwanza, Tanzania

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Abstract

Supplier orientation's role in augmenting firms' performance is gaining increasing attention from scholars. However, empirical research examining this relationship remains limited. Examination of the effects of supplier orientation dimensions on SMEs' performance in the sector involved in furniture manufacturing in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania was undertaken, focusing on the mediating role of customer loyalty. Using a quantitative correlational design, data from 350 furniture manufacturing SMEs through a cross-sectional questionnaire-based survey were attained. By employing covariance-based structural equation modelling, the analysis revealed that customer loyalty partially acted as a mediator between supplier orientation dimensions and furniture-manufacturing SMEs performance relationships. Notably, collaborative relationships with suppliers exhibited the strongest positive indirect effect on furniture-manufacturing SMEs performance ($\beta = 0.1621$), followed by information sharing with suppliers ($\beta = 0.1265$). In contrast, supplier evaluation and selection exhibited the weakest indirect effect ($\beta = 0.0543$). The outcomes stipulate the importance of fostering long-term collaborative relationships and effective information sharing with suppliers to enhance customer loyalty and drive superior firm performance. The furniture manufacturing SMEs should prioritise in building long-term supplier collaborations that create synergy for open communication and value co-creation to nurture customer loyalty and, consequently, drive superior firm performance.

Keywords: Collaborative relationship with suppliers, furniture manufacturing SMEs, information sharing with suppliers, supplier orientation, supplier evaluation and selection.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: gordianbwemelo@gmail.com

Introduction

For years, market orientation has been acknowledged as a crucial strategic imperative for achieving superior performance in business firms (Correia et al., 2021). Market orientation is concerned with the capability of a firm to generate market intelligence and creatively utilise it to create value (Kohli and Jaworski, 1990). Building on Narver and Slater (1990) seminal work, market orientation comprises of gathering, disseminating, and responding to market intelligence across three main dimensions: customer orientation, inter-functional coordination, and competitor orientation (Boateng et al., 2024). However, given the interconnected nature of modern supply chains, the traditional framework for market orientation (Narver and Slater, 1990) has been challenged for insufficiently addressing upstream relationships with suppliers for the firms to be truly market oriented. Accordingly, scholars have formulated an extended market orientation model that recognises the role of supplier orientation (SupO) in catalysing firm performance (Aslam et al., 2024; Alhakimi & Mahmoud, 2020).

Aljafari *et al.* (2017) conceptualised SupO as a firm's strategic endeavour in creation of value by engaging and collaborating with suppliers. SupO is particularly critical in resource-constrained and supply-chain-dependent sectors, as it enables firms to acquire essential resources, technical skills, and technologies from suppliers in prioritization of time and cost-effective emphasis (Liu *et al.*, 2024; Celikyay *et al.*, 2023; Gebisa, 2023). Its implementation performs important function in boosting production efficiency, mitigating supply chain uncertainties, fostering innovation, and delivery of superior products at competitive prices (Ofori & Appiah-Nimo, 2023; Nenavani & Jain, 2022).

SupO is particularly essential in resource-constrained and supply-chain-dependent sectors, where operational efficiency, quality and cost competitiveness are supreme for survival and growth. The furniture manufacturing industry is a foremost example. Companies like IKEA & Ashely prove significant role of SupO in their rise to become world-leading retail furniture brands (Faircloth, 2021). By embracing SupO, these companies have optimised their supply chains, enhanced their innovation capabilities and maintained cost efficiency without sacrificing quality (Faircloth, 2021). In developing countries, such as Vietnam and Malaysia, furniture manufacturing companies exploit versatile sourcing marketplaces, strong supply chains, and participation of suppliers across the manufacturing cycle (DuyFuraka, 2023). Consequently, these countries have emerged as major players in global furniture exports.

Furniture manufacturing sector is a vital labour-intensive in the global economy, contributing to 4 percent of the world's production and provides employment opportunities of 3 percent of the global workforce (Koridze, 2022). The sector is experiencing steady growth driven by urbanisation, population growth, technological advancements, and quantitative growth of businesses established (Statista, 2024; Rame *et al.*, 2023; Koridze, 2022). The global furniture market is projected to grow substantially, with the sector's value expected to reach USD 799.5 billion by 2025, approaching USD 800 billion in 2026 (Statista, 2024).

In Africa, the furniture industry demonstrates growth potential, with several countries positioned to expand furniture production for both internal consumption and exports.

Driven by the rapidly growing urban population, the demand for residential and commercial furnishings continues to rise and the furniture business continues to boom in many African markets. By 2050, it is expected that approximately 1.3 billion people will be living in Africa, with the sub-Saharan region projected to add more than 500 million people migrating to urban areas by 2020 (Africa Business Pages, 2025). Therefore, an increase in demand for housing and business furniture will drive the industry towards sustained growth.

In Tanzania, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) largely over dominate in the furniture manufacturing sub-sector, most of which are informal (Guadagno *et al.*, 2019). This sub-sector is critical in facilitating industrialisation, job creation and income generation. It accounts for 9.9% of all manufacturing establishments in the country (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2024). Additionally, this sub-sector represents around 6% of the country's total manufacturing workforce and is well positioned to increase furniture sales locally and internationally (Guadagno *et al.*, 2019). The furniture market in Tanzania is anticipated to raise steadily, with an estimated revenue in 2025 equal to \$606.03 million with a compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) equal to 1.37% from 2025 to 2029 (Statista, 2024). The increasing trend of urbanisation, along with the growth of middle class, continues to rise demand for furniture, encouraging many entrepreneurs to venture into furniture business.

Despite the potential for market growth, Tanzania's furniture manufacturing SMEs (FM-SMEs) remain underdeveloped due to high levels of informality, inadequate access to quality raw materials, and increasing competition from both local and imported furniture. Many FM-SMEs struggle with operational inefficiencies and innovation due to fragmented supply chains and a lack of strategic partnerships with suppliers. They intensively depend on raw materials like wood, metal, and textiles, characterized by undependable supply and logistical inefficiencies, leading to supply disruptions, production delays, quality inconsistencies, and higher operational costs (Guadagno *et al.*, 2019). As a result, the majority of furniture manufacturers are progressively obligated to use semi-processed wood products sourced from other countries, such as Mozambique and the Democratic Republic of Congo (Guadagno *et al.*, 2019). While some firms have turned towards using alternative imported materials such as metals and textiles, strategic sourcing and processing capabilities are still not well established, leading to higher operational costs, supply disruptions and production delays (Mwagike, 2024; Guadagno *et al.*, 2019).

Likewise, Tanzania's FM-SMEs are facing increasing competition from larger domestic firms and a growing entry of furniture imported largely from China and Malaysia (Kumburu & Kessy, 2021). This trend is accompanied with consumers' preference for imported furniture, which are often perceived as being of higher quality, better design, superior finishing, competitive pricing, and a wider range of products (Mwagike, 2024; Kumburu and Kessy, 2021). Local manufacturers struggle with issues such as high prices, inferior finishing, limited variety, and long waiting time from ordering to delivery. These limitations stem primarily from high costs of raw materials and production, poor technology, and inadequate ability to innovate (Mwagike, 2024; Guadagno *et al.*, 2019).

The aforementioned challenges highlight the necessity of SupO as a strategic intervention to mitigate supply chain uncertainties, and enhance operational efficiency, co-innovation capabilities, and high-quality and competitively priced products, ultimately enhancing the performance of FM-SMEs. Moreover, research shows that any strategic orientation is ineffective unless the business can build and maintain a stable customer base, which is largely a result of customer loyalty (LOY) (Amoah, 2024; Rajagukguk *et al.*, 2024; Ismail, 2022).

LOY refers to the extent to which customers consistently choose and remain dedicated to the firm and its products (Albarq, 2023). LOY has been recognised for a long time as a cornerstone for measuring firms' performance. Loyal customers are the backbone of a firm's revenue stream as they make repeat purchases, are less likely to switch to competitors, provide constructive feedback, are likely to pay premium prices, and recommend products to others (Amoah, 2024). Integrating SupO with initiatives to enhance LOY is crucial, especially for SMEs because of their limited marketing budgets for acquiring new customers.

Despite the acknowledged importance of SupO in enhancing firm performance, empirical studies examining its effect through LOY as a mediator are limited, particularly within the context of SMEs (Alhakimi & Mahmoud, 2020). The concentration of the previous research has been on how supplier engagement practices influence firm performance but do not account for LOY's mediation role (Liu *et al.*, 2024; Celikyay *et al.*, 2023; Israel, 2022). The research thus is set out to address the identified gap where examination of the LOY's mediation effect that associates SupO and firm performance in the Tanzania's FM-SMEs perspective.

Underpinning Theory

The theoretical framework was grounded in Supply Chain Integration Theory (SCIT), propounded by Flynn *et al.* (2010). SCIT posts that greater performance is resulting from the integrated supply chain processes of the firm internally and with the external upstream and downstream partners. This integration is concerned with aligning and coordinating activities like sourcing, procurement, production, distribution, and customer service to ensure seamless and efficient flow of information and products (Flynn *et al.*, 2010). Supply chain integration can enhance firm performance through cost saving, optimal operational efficiencies, improved product quality and responsiveness to market demands, and enhanced LOY (Antora & Raihan, 2024; Yadav *et al.*, 2023; Negi, 2021).

SCIT is a relevant theoretical framework for examining the role of SupO in catalyzing Tanzania's FM-SMEs by addressing challenges such as supply chain disruptions, high operational costs, and limited innovation capabilities. If effectively incorporated, SupO can help FM-SMEs access essential resources like raw materials and technical expertise more efficiently. This can result in improving operational efficiency, enhanced innovation capabilities, and better product quality, all of which are crucial for building LOY and enhancing higher performance in an extremely competitive market (Antora & Raihan, 2024). Through performing examination of LOY's position in mediating the connection between SupO and firms' performance, the research aims at providing understandings

among SMEs on how to strategically integrate suppliers to advance their competitiveness in the market.

Numerous empirical studies have applied SCIT in examining how supply chain integration capabilities produced superior performance. For instance, in the context of manufacturing firms in Bangladesh, Antora & Raihan (2024) established that an integration between suppliers and customers positively impacted financial performance. Hendijani and Saeidi Saei (2020) presented that supply chain integration significantly enhanced financial performance in Iran's automotive and steel industries. Likewise, Uwamahoro (2018) established that integration between internal and customers meaningfully enhanced the manufacturing firms' performance in Rwanda. These studies affirm SCIT's applicability to resource-constrained, high-competition environments like Tanzania's FM-SMEs, where strategic supply chain coordination is pivotal for survival and growth.

Empirical Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Supplier Orientation within Market Orientation Framework

Traditional conceptualisation of market orientation is fixed in the work of Kohli and Jaworski (1990), who defined it as process of generating, disseminating, and acting in a responsiveness manner to market intelligence. Further, the emphasis was made on market orientation to comprise of customer, competitor, and inter-functional coordination orientations core dimensions (Narver and Slater, 1990). These components enable firms to recognize and act accordingly to customers' needs, monitor competitive dynamics, and ensure coordinated internal activities for delivering superior value. However, scholars have argued that the traditional market orientation model overlooks upstream stakeholders (suppliers) whose role in value co-creation and firm performance is critical in today's complex and interdependent supply chain ecosystems. To address this limitation, the conceptual scope of market orientation has been extended to include orientation towards suppliers (Aslam *et al.*, 2024; Alhakimi & Mahmoud, 2020). This shift replicates the rising acknowledgment that value creation is not only the outcome of downstream aspects in the market orientation framework but also SupO.

In this study, the broadened view focusing specifically on SupO was adopted due to its relevance in resource-dependent sectors such as furniture manufacturing. Unlike customer and competitor orientation, which emphasise downstream responsiveness, SupO addresses the upstream relational dynamics that influence production continuity, cost efficiency, product innovation, satisfaction level of customers, and ultimately business achievement. In the context of Tanzanian FM-SMEs, where supply chains are often fragmented, informal, and vulnerable to disruptions, SupO becomes not merely supportive but foundational to survival and competitive performance. The inter-functional coordination as an integral part of the dimensions is often viewed less fitting in studies involving SMEs following their informal internal processes and simpler structures (Hübnerová *et al.*, 2020).

Impact of Supplier Orientation on Firm Performance

Previous studies suggest that firms that actively engage with their suppliers are well positioned to engage in value co-creation, reduce uncertainty, and enhance operational agility. For instance, Celikyay *et al.* (2023) established that SupO is well aligned with strategies concerning with differentiation and cost leadership, both of which lead to superior performance. In their study of Turkey's ICT sector, Celikyay *et al.* (2023) found that SupO promotes supplier-driven innovations, leading to better financial performance. Similarly, Alhakimi & Mahmoud (2020) found that SupO performs an important function in boosting competitiveness through innovation and differentiation strategies among SMEs in Yemen. Andersen (2021) upholds SupO practices can facilitate dynamic capabilities development and enhance innovation capabilities which eventually lead to superior performance.

While SupO is recognised as a significant driver of firm performance, it is often approached as a unidimensional construct. Such oversimplification can result in a partial understanding of the distinct roles SupO dimensions in driving firm performance. SupO can enhance firm performance in different distinct mechanisms, each playing a unique role. Thus, adopting a multidimensional perspective on SupO is indispensable for unlocking deeper insights into how various aspects of SupO drive firm performance (Diandra & Azmy, 2021).

One of the key dimensions of SupO is information sharing with suppliers (ISS). It is concerned with the exchange of timely, accurate, and relevant information between firms and their suppliers. Information is a valuable input in identifying and acclimatising with business environment fluctuations and uncertainties. Numerous studies have attested how ISS impacts firms' performance. A study by Gebisa (2023) uncovered that ISS enhances supply chain integration by fostering trust, reducing uncertainties, and improving operational efficiency, which established are essential for achieving superior performance. Similarly, Celikyay *et al.* (2023) that uninterrupted information flow rises supply chain agility, promotes collaborative innovation, and increases operational effectiveness, which in turn translate into firm performance.

Another critical dimension of SupO is supplier evaluation and selection (SES). SES provides firms with an understanding of suppliers who are performing well based on criteria such as quality of raw materials, delivery reliability, cost efficiency, and geographical proximity. SES lessens the risks associated with uncertainties in the supply of raw materials, which subsequently improves product quality and reduces production costs, which in turn, enhances superior performance (Milovanović & Milenović, 2022).

Although SES is essential, literature highlights limitations of its strategic scope. SES is often criticised for its transactional nature, which possibly limits its ability to influence relational outcomes like customer satisfaction and loyalty (Shikhalizade, 2024). The relationship called transactional always depress suppliers from contributing to new ideas or innovations that are beneficial to both parties due to its focus on making transaction and disregarding customer relationships. To optimise the effectiveness of SES, building and maintaining collaborative relationships with suppliers (CRS) becomes imperative.

CRS performs a vital function in responsiveness and the designing of product which in turn results in customers' satisfaction and loyalty. Stekelorum *et al.* (2022) contend CRS hinges on knowledge sharing, joint problem-solving, and coordinated efforts to facilitate innovation and co-creation of value that firms would not be able to create alone. Suppliers are more likely to offer cost-saving ideas, align the operations with buyer needs, adapt to market changes, hence, enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty (Canbul and Çemberci, 2024; Hanafiah *et al.*, 2019).

The implementation of ISS, SES, and CRS practices presents a strategic opportunity for FM-SMEs to overcome raw material sourcing challenges and enhance performance. FM-SMEs have to cope with challenges such as resource constraints and fluctuating material availability. ISS practices can help FM-SMEs improve coordination with suppliers, reduce lead times, and optimize inventory management. By assessing and selecting suppliers based on performance metrics, FM-SMEs can reduce supply chain risks, increase operational efficiency, and ensure quality in the products, resulting in enhanced performance. FM-SMEs can access resources, technical expertise, and industry insights that are often beyond their internal capabilities (Audretsch *et al.*, 2023, Sulisty, 2020). Therefore, this study hypothesizes the following:

H₁: ISS has a positive effect on the FM-SMEs' performance.

H₂: SES has a positive effect on FM-SMEs' performance.

H₃: CRS positively impacts the FM-SMEs' performance.

Customer Loyalty and Firm Performance

Today's business environment exceedingly competitive has made LOY a key business imperative for every forward-looking business that desires to survive and operate successfully. Whether SupO can help improve firm performance depends on the capability of firms in building and retaining a stable customer base. A stable customer base is vibrant for enhanced firms' performance, as sales volume grew from re-purchases benefits in increasing market share and improve organisation's profitability (Oiku *et al.*, 2023). LOY is expressed through behavioural and attitudinal commitments. The behavioural commitment manifests itself in observable actions like positive word-of-mouth, re-purchase intention, readiness to withstand a few negatives, willingness to pay premium prices, and resistance to switching (Na *et al.*, 2023; Atulkar, 2020). Conversely, the attitudinal dimension reflects emotional aspects such as feelings, preference, and trust (Atulkar, 2020). Since this study relies on perceived loyalty as reported by furniture manufacturers rather than direct customer feedback, it focuses on the behavioural aspects of LOY.

According to Arslan (2020), businesses that have loyal consumers find it easier to deal with competition because they receive a steady stream of revenue from loyal customers and act as brand ambassadors through referrals. Many studies have shown that loyal customers mostly participate in spreading positive word-of-mouth, making re-purchase, and having lower switching intentions (Ismail 2022; Sampaio *et al.*, 2020). Sampaio *et al.* (2020) exposed positive and significant connection between LOY and hotel industry's

performance. In line with this, the literature review by Ismail (2022) identified a significant amount of evidence indicating that LOY is one of the factors driving business success, as it results in higher sales, profitability, and market share. Overall, the literature establishes a strong relationship between LOY and firms' performance. Thus, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H₄: LOY positively and significantly affects FM-SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam.

Supplier Orientation and Customer Loyalty

In the standpoint of the competitive challenges facing the furniture manufacturing industry, developing strategies for enhancing LOY is crucial. According to the literature, SupO leads to effective supply chain management, which is vital for maintaining customer satisfaction and ensuring LOY sustainability (Nguyen Thi & Nguyen Thi Thu, 2022; Ahmed, 2021; Bragin *et al.*, 2020). Supplier orientation also leads to better coordination and responsiveness within supply chains. Collaboration and ISS allow firms to enhance product quality, minimize expenses, and deliver within a specified timeline, which is crucial for maintaining LOY (Ahmed, 2021; Bragin *et al.*, 2020).

Thomya *et al.* (2023) in Thailand discovered that ISS enables firms to detect supply chain disruptions earlier, respond promptly to customer demands, minimize production downtime, and hence improve customer satisfaction, which is a precursor to LOY. Liu *et al.* (2024) also confirmed that seamless sharing of information among all partners creates collaborative partnerships, innovations, and a means to react and respond to changing market conditions. Thus, collaboration and ISS can support innovation in furniture design and enhance product quality, enabling FM-SMEs in Tanzania to compete effectively in both home-grown and foreign markets.

Ahmed (2021) investigated the how the practices in the supply chain management influence satisfaction and retention of customers in large companies operating in retail food sector in the Southern Saudi Arabia. Strategic supplier partnership statistically was estimated to cause a significant and positive effect on customer satisfaction, which antecedently enhances customer retention. Another empirical study by Amoah (2024), which examined how collaborative efforts among actors of the supply chain impacted the Ghanaian customer satisfaction and loyalty, established that firms that actively engage their suppliers as strategic partners yield superior levels of LOY. The results affiliate with those found by Zaid *et al.* (2021), who resolved that collaboration with suppliers has a significant direct effect on LOY.

Liu *et al.* (2024) suggest that collaborative and joint approaches with suppliers to identify innovative opportunities to deliver enhanced value to customers is critically important for any firm. To do this, companies should have systems in place to track and assess suppliers' practices and capabilities to ensure that they deliver quality raw materials at reasonable prices and when they need them. They also have to ensure a good relationship with suppliers who can provide goods that are acceptable in quality, price, and delivery.

In this study, the effect of SupO on LOY is examined in the Tanzanian context with a special focus on FM-SMEs. This study is considered relevant because of the dependency of FM-SMEs on raw material suppliers. This leads to the proposition that creating greater customer value using innovative opportunities born from a supplier and a firm's ability to monitor and evaluate suppliers' practices and capabilities represents a strategic resource aimed at contributing substantively to a firm's greater performance. Therefore, the research hypothesizes the following:

H5: ISS positively influences LOY.

H6: SES positively influences LOY.

H7: CRS positively influences LOY.

Mediating Effect of Customer Loyalty on Supplier Orientation-Firm Performance Relationship

Building on the established importance of LOY in driving business performance, the literature suggests that the benefits of strong SupO can be amplified through the mediating role of LOY (Amoah, 2024; Rajagukguk *et al.*, 2024; Tenreng *et al.*, 2019). The main cause is that effective supplier collaboration can lead to consistent product quality, reliable service, and positive customer experiences, which, in turn, foster LOY (Nguyen Thi & Nguyen Thi Thu, 2022). This aligns with the broader view that LOY performs mediating function on how supplier management and firms' performance related to each other (Nadason *et al.*, 2024).

For example, in the Vietnamese household electronics sector, Nguyen Thi & Nguyen Thi Thu (2022) provide empirical support showing that supply chain collaboration is positively related to LOY, which subsequently enhances firm performance. Their findings highlight the of supplier relationships in enhancing customer experience, which paves the way for enhanced loyalty and performance. However, limited empirical inquiry has been given to the effect of distinct components of SupO on firm performance via LOY. Rajagukguk *et al.* (2024) emphasises the concern for extra empirical studies in examining the correlation between SupO and firm performance through LOY. To fill this gap, the research hypothesises the following:

H8: LOY mediates the nexus between ISS and FM-SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam.

H9: LOY mediates the nexus between SES and FM-SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam.

H10: LOY mediates the nexus between CRS and FM-SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam.

Although alternative mediators such as customer satisfaction or innovation may also be conceptually valid, this study deliberately focuses on LOY for two key reasons. First, LOY signifies the behavioural outcome of customer satisfaction and trust, making it a more proximal indicator of sustained business performance. In contrast, satisfaction may

not always translate into repeat purchase or advocacy behaviour unless reinforced by loyalty (Liu *et al.*, 2024). Second, innovation depends more on internal firm capabilities and take longer to realise its effects. Given the resource constraints and operational realities of FM-SMEs, loyalty is more practically relevant in explaining how SupO translates into improved firm performance.

Conceptual Framework

In reference to the reviewed literature and the proposed hypotheses, conceptualization of a framework was undertaken to explain the relationships among the variables. The framework considers SupO dimensions as predictor variables, with both direct effects on FM-SMEs performance and indirect effects mediated by LOY as illustrated in Figure 1. Arrows indicate the expected positive influence of each construct, aligned with hypotheses H1 to H10.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Research Methods

Research Approach

The research implemented a correlational research design, utilising a quantitative approach in assessing the hypothesised relations among variables. The correlational design was opted since the research aimed at examining relationships without manipulating the variables, aligning with Gawali's, (2023) recommendations.

Dar es Salam region was purposively chosen for this study because it serves as Tanzania's commercial hub and hosts the largest number of FM-SMEs (Kumburu *et al.*, 2019). The competitive market environment driven by the large number of local producers and imported furniture in this region provides a unique strategic setting to

examine how FM-SMEs can manage competitive pressures and leverage LOY to improve their market position.

The research made adoption of a dual stratified random sampling procedure, using district and business size as the stratification criteria. The sampling frame comprised 1,062 FM-SMEs derived from the 2015 industrial production survey conducted by the NBS in collaboration with the Ministry of Industry and Trade (MIT). The survey report indicates the distribution of FM-SMEs across the districts: Ilala with 223, Kigamboni with 53, Kinondoni with 203, Temeke with 423, and Ubungu with 156. While the 2015 survey report is ten years old, it still serves as the latest comprehensive source of information on manufacturing establishments in mainland Tanzania. The Industrial Production Census would be a potential source, but it was last conducted in 2013, and the next census is currently in progress, making the 2015 survey report the latest source. To enhance the validity of the sampling frame, telephone calls were made to the listed contact numbers to verify their current operational status and willingness to participate.

The original size of the sample was estimated to be 291 adopting Yamane's (1967) for finite populations, with a 5% margin of error, which is well known research aligned with social sciences when population size is known. To account for potential nonresponse bias, a draft of the questionnaire underwent a pre-testing activity including a sample of 30 respondents before proceeding to the actual administration of the questionnaire. The pre-test revealed a 20% nonresponse rate, which necessitated adjusting the sample size to maintain statistical power and validity. An adjusted sample size of 364 was obtained by dividing the original sample size (291) by the response rate (80%), as recommended by Kish (2005).

Based on the adjusted sample size of 364, the distribution of the sample across districts was determined in accordance to the proportions of the total FM-SMEs population in the region, as follows: Temeke (146), Ilala (76), Kinondoni (70), Ubungu (54), and Kigamboni (18). This was essential to ensure sufficient representation of FM-SMEs for each district, as the competitive landscape and raw material accessibility may vary across districts.

Given the dynamic nature of SMEs, reliance on a single stratification criterion might limit the generalisability of the study. To address this, the second level of stratification was based on enterprise size, categorised as micro, small, and medium enterprises. Categorisation was conducted during data collection based on respondents' disclosure of business characteristics. Of the 350 valid responses used for analysis, 88 (25.1%) were micro enterprises, 221(63.1%) were small enterprises, and 41 (11.7%) were medium enterprises.

Measurement of Variables and Data Collection

The research formulated measurement of variables and structural models consisting of five constructs: ISS, SES, CRS, LOY, and FM-SMEs performance. Each construct was operationalised using items adapted from various prior studies to ensure their relevance to the context of Tanzanian FM-SMEs (Table 1).

Table 1: Measurement of Model Variables

Construct	Number of items	Source
ISS	Five	(Muthuswamy & Al-ameryeen, 2022; Silva & Moreira, 2021)
SES	Six	(Muthuswamy & Al-ameryeen, 2022; Silva & Moreira, 2021)
CRS	Seven	(Muthuswamy & Al-ameryeen, 2022; Silva & Moreira, 2021)
LOY	Five	(Ismail, 2022; Sampaio <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
FM-SMEs Performance	Twelve	(Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020a; Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020b; Forth & Bryson, 2019)

A wide-ranging review of prevailing literature was performed to classify items that effectively capture the constructs of SupO, LOY, and firm performance. Items for each construct were reviewed and refined to reflect the operational realities of FM-SMEs in Tanzania. The pre-testing undertaken covered 30 respondents, the aim was to allow the identification of issues with the items, leading to refinement of item wording and terminology to ensure clarity and contextual relevance. Feedback from the pre-test indicated that all items were clearly understood, and only minimal rewording was required. The internal consistency of the pre-test responses was also estimated, yielding acceptable reliability scores (all Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.70$).

The items opted were measured by adopting the Likert scale in five-point options extending from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'. The option for this scale was based on methodological considerations and the respondents' backgrounds. The use of less than 5-point scale would simplify respondents' views, forcing them to choose the nearest best alternative and potentially result in measurement errors. On the other hand, a 5-point scale would add complexity, resulting in rushed or inaccurate answers. The 5-point strikes a balance between measurement sensitivity and respondent fatigue, making it ideal for many studies. Moreover, the findings from the pre-test indicated that the respondents found the five-point scale appropriate.

The study utilized composite measures derived from five indicators - sales growth, employee growth, asset growth, profit growth, and market share growth to capture the multidimensional nature of firm performance. These indicators are widely recognised and commonly used for assessing SMEs' performance (Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020a; Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020b; Forth & Bryson, 2019; Neneh, 2018)). Given SMEs' general reluctance to share financial data and the limited availability of such records (Jalali *et al.*, 2020; Duygulu *et al.*, 2016), subjective performance measures were selected for this study. Vij & Bedi (2016) revealed the reliability and validity of subjective measures, noting their strong correlation with objective measures in assessing SMEs performance.

While subjective measures have been shown to correlate reasonably with objective performance and are widely used in SMEs research, the risk of self-report bias was anticipated. To mitigate self-report bias, confidentiality and anonymity were granted to respondents to encourage honest responses. Moreover, items were carefully worded to

capture relative performance rather than absolute figures to reduce social desirability effects. Data collectors were trained to create understanding of the research aim and to encourage participants to provide thoughtful and accurate responses.

A cross-sectional survey was performed among owners or managers of FM-SMEs using questionnaires. The survey method was used because it is possible to collect plenty of data effectively and quickly at a relatively low cost. FM-SMEs were chosen because managers or owners are the main players on whom the main decisions rest, and they usually monitor all the operations of their enterprises. Therefore, they were viewed as more knowledgeable about their firms' workflows and practices. Telephone calls were made to the listed contact numbers to verify the present availability of these firms and to obtain permission for data access.

In regard to the concern that data on the predictor, mediating, and criterion variables were simultaneously gathered from similar respondents, using the same instrument (questionnaire) and consistent response format (ordinal scales), common method bias (CMB) was anticipated. Such a bias could either expand or reduce associations among variables, thus compromising research findings' validity and reliability (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). To mitigate CMB, construct measurement items from multiple sources were adapted, questionnaires were administered on-site to the respondents, thereby facilitating immediate clarification of any ambiguity in the questionnaire that would result in misinterpretation and careless responses. Additionally, respondents were assured of confidentiality and anonymity, thereby reducing potential bias.

Ethical Considerations

Although ethical approval was not necessary, all research procedures adhered to the principles of good research practice. Respondents were notified concerning the objective of the research and assurance was warranted for voluntary participation and the responses provided would be utilized solely for academic integrity and reported in aggregate form to ensure anonymity. Before data collection, telephone calls were made to the listed contact numbers to obtain voluntary informed consent.

Data Analysis

The initial step involved a statistical assessment of the CMB whereby, Herman's single-factor test was applied. The rule of thumb is that, for the data not to have the CMB, the first component should account for less than 50% of the total variability in the original dataset (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). Additionally, the Common Latent Factor (CLF) approach was adopted in estimating the potential CMB within the structural model. This approach involved loading all observed variables onto a single unmeasured latent method factor in addition to their theoretical constructs (Williams & Anderson, 1994). The standardized regression weights of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) model with CLF were compared against those without CLF. A difference of less than 0.2 between the standardized loadings across the two models suggests the absence of CBM (Conway & Lance, 2010). This dual-method assessment increases confidence in the results' validity.

Subsequent to the statistical Harman's one-factor test, testing for fitness of dataset to factor analysis was performed. This was done by measuring the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value and conducting Bartlett's test of sphericity to determine the sample's adequacy and the presence of correlations among the items in the dataset. A KMO coefficient approaching 1 would signify fittingness of the dataset to factor analysis, whereas a value less than 0.5 would indicate inadequate factors (Khairi *et al.*, 2021). Further, a the significant results in the Bartlett's test ($p < 0.05$) would signify that the variables are related and suitable for structure detection (Khairi *et al.*, 2021).

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was performed preceding to CFA. While CFA is typically sufficient for validated measures, EFA was deemed necessary because the items for measurement were adapted from preceding research. Conducting the EFA provided an opportunity to validate the adapted measurement items within the Tanzanian FM-SMEs context, where the scales had not previously been applied. EFA was performed by subjecting all measurement items to unrotated Principal Component Analysis (PCA). As part of the EFA process, only items whose factor loadings exceeding 0.5 were retained, which is a standard practice in factor analysis.

Following the EFA, CFA was performed to validate the final measurement models. CFA and covariance-based structural equation modelling (CB-SEM) analysis were executed via Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) version 23 software. AMOS was specifically desired for the validation of complex structures, such as mediating effects and path relationships. CB-SEM was a suitable alternative to partial least squares-SME (PLS-SEM) because of its superior suitability for theory testing, which is ideal for assessing the overall fit of the structural model and for testing complex relationships among latent constructs (Vinkóczy *et al.*, 2024; Hair *et al.*, 2019). This choice was further justified by size of the sample and data normality assumptions.

The study specifically utilised bootstrapping consisting of 5,000 samples at a 95 percent confidence interval to analyse the LOY's mediating effect on how SupO dimensions and FM-SMEs' performance relate to one another. The choice of 5,000 bootstrap samples is supported by statistical literature, which suggests that a minimum of 5,000 resamples provides stable and reliable estimations of the indirect effects and their allied confidence intervals (Preacher & Hayes, 2008). A confidence interval that excludes zero suggests mediation effect to be interpreted statistically significant, indicating that customer loyalty performs a meaningful function in explaining how supplier orientation and firms' performance are associated.

Internal consistency reliability was judged by the use of the Composite Reliability (CR), with coefficients beyond 0.7 are judged acceptable (Hair *et al.*, 2019). CR is particularly recommended in SEM context-based studies as it provides an extreme accurate measure of internal consistency (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The analysis used Average Variance Extracted (AVE) to assess convergent validity for every construct, requiring a minimum value of 0.5. The divergent (Discriminant) validity analysis was accrued out to establish the distinctiveness of the constructs. The square root of the AVE for every construct was compared with the inter-correlation coefficients between the constructs. Divergent validity was established when the square root of the AVE for every construct exceeded its correlation with other constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Results and Discussion

Response Rate

364 questionnaires were administered and received back forming 100% response rate. Exclusion of 14 questionnaires in the final analysis was considered practical since they had excessive missing data. Therefore, 350 complete and usable questionnaires were processed for the next step analysis, leading into a valid response rate of 96.2%. This high response rate increases the validity of the results and decreases the bias for nonresponse.

Common Method Bias Analysis

The test for Harman's single-factor that was undertaken revealed that both the first unrotated and rotated factors, which present the largest variability in the original dataset were below the 50% threshold endorsed by Podsakoff *et al.* (2003). Specifically, the first factor which was not rotated accounted for 39.2%, while the rotated first factor counted 16.2% of the total variance. The results suggest that CBM was unlikely to significantly distort the observed relationships among the constructs. Further validation using the CLF approach indicated that the differences between standardized regression weights for each of the observed variables in the models with and without the CLF were minimally below 0.2. Since all differences remained below the recommended cut-off of 0.20, these findings reinforce the conclusion that CMB was not a solemn issue of interest in this research.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Factor analysis using PCA with Varimax rotation confirmed the appropriateness of the dataset for the EFA. The results indicated excellent adequacy of sampling as justified with KMO coefficient of 0.95 and significant Bartlett's test ($\chi^2 = 8026.1, p < 0.001$), with determinant 4.379E-11. The rotated component matrix, presented in Table 2 revealed distinct components with significant loadings for various items.

Following the Varimax rotation, six components were identified, deletion of items with factor loadings under 0.5 was executed as they might lead to poor convergent validity (Arifin & Yusoff, 2016) and factors with fewer than three items were excluded, resulting in 33 items grouped into five components for further analysis. For instance, the FP12 with a negative factor loading implies to have a negative contribution in the variance of the particular construct and hence considered to be weak. If the FP12 is deleted, then the 6th construct remains with only one item (FP11) which is out of the minimum requirement of at least 2 items. The identification of the two overlapping items (FP11 and FP12) underlined with the researchers suspects of the significant difference of the potential factor structure, hence the need of conducting EFA rather than directly employing CFA (Tavakol & Wetzel, 2020). This process enhanced the measurement and structural models' validity in later stages of analysis as the adopted items would have been tested in different populations, context as well as conditions.

Table 2: Rotated Component Matrix Indicating Items' Factor Loadings

Code	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
FP4	0.724					
FP5	0.713					
FP6	0.705					
FP2	0.657					
FP8	0.642					
FP1	0.641					
FP9	0.616					
FP7	0.615					
FP10	0.614					
FP3	0.603					
CRS2		0.816				
CRS1		0.815				
CRS6		0.748				
CRS4		0.741				
CRS3		0.728				
CRS5		0.727				
CRS7		0.626				
SES6			0.823			
SES5			0.781			
SES2			0.780			
SES3			0.756			
SES4			0.755			
SES1			0.743			
ISS1				0.838		
ISS2				0.838		
ISS3				0.837		
ISS4				0.820		
ISS5				0.561		
LOY3					0.726	
LOY1					0.724	
LOY2					0.665	
LOY4					0.637	
LOY5					0.616	
FP11						0.709
FP12						-0.556

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Analytical Test for Reliability and Validity

The reliability and validity assessments confirmed that all five constructs were psychometrically sound. The study revealed that all five constructs attained high reliability, with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients surpassing 0.7 (extending from 0.872 for

LOY to 0.921 for CRS). For convergent validity, three constructs (ISS, CRS, SES) met the AVE threshold of 0.5, while FP (0.428) and LOY (0.456) fell slightly below. Despite the lower AVE values, both constructs exhibited $CR > 0.70$, and all standardized factor loadings exceeded 0.60, indicating strong internal consistency (Juanamasta *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, model fit indices at both the measurement and structural levels confirmed that the overall model was acceptable and stable. Nonetheless, this limitation is acknowledged, and future studies are encouraged to refine measurement items or use multi-method approaches to enhance convergent validity. The results confirm that the measurement model is internally consistent and valid, with items reliably capturing their intended latent constructs (Table 3).

Table 3: Constructs' Reliability and Validity

Construct	No. of items	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE
FM-SME' Performance	10	0.918	0.882	0.428
LOY	5	0.872	0.806	0.456
ISS	5	0.910	0.888	0.618
CRS	7	0.921	0.897	0.556
SES	6	0.901	0.899	0.598

The high CR and AVE values indicate that the constructs, as operationalized with the items in Appendix, were reliable and valid. The results confirmed that the items under every construct were consistent and accurately captured the fundamental latent variables.

Moreover, the divergent validity was assessed using the HTMT. The rule of thumb to conclude the attainment of divergent validity is that the HTMT is always under 0.85 (Henseler *et al.*, 2015). For this study, the HTMT ranged between 0.31 for ISS and SES to 0.66 for ISS and FP implying that the overall HTMT values were below 0.85 for each of the pairs of the corresponding study constructs (Table 4).

Table 4: Assessment of Divergent Validity Using HTMT

	FP	SES	CRS
SES	0.49		
CRS	0.65	0.53	
ISS	0.66	0.31	0.47

Confirming the Measurement Models for the Study Constructs

The CFA outputs expressed that each measurement model confirmed tolerable fit with the observed data. Although the chi-square tests were significant, the proportion of chi-square to degrees of freedom (χ^2/df) for all models was below the recommended threshold of 3. For instance, ISS ($\chi^2/df = 9.654/5 = 1.931$), SES ($10.781/7 = 1.54$), CRS ($27.791/13 = 2.14$), and LOY ($13.937/5 = 2.79$) all indicating good model fit.

Furthermore, the fit indices for all constructs exceeded the minimum criteria. For instance, Comparative Fit Index (CFI) coefficients oscillated from 0.989 to 0.997, and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) values ranged from 0.965 to 0.993—both well above the 0.90

threshold. The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) coefficients were low and appropriate: ISS = 0.052, SES = 0.039, CRS = 0.057, and LOY = 0.072, all under the maximum cut-off of 0.08. Similarly, the Residual Mean Square (RMR) values were satisfactory: ISS = 0.016, SES = 0.019, CRS = 0.024, and LOY = 0.023.

Assumptions of the SEM

Before proceeding with the SEM analysis, key assumptions, such as multivariate normality, linearity, and absence of multicollinearity, were checked and found to be satisfied. The skewness values for all variables fell under -3 and +3, whereas kurtosis coefficients fell under the acceptable coefficients of -10 to +10, satisfying the multivariate normality assumption (Brown, 2015). The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values were underneath 10, and levels for tolerance exceeded 0.1, confirming the absence of multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2019). The scatterplots exhibited linear patterns confirming linearity of the links among the variables.

Along with the SEM assumptions, summary statistics were assessed with respect to the R-squared and F-tests. Table 5 reveals that ISS, SES, CRS, and LOY explained approximately 61% of the variance in FM-SME performance.

Table 5: Model Summary Statistics on R-Squared Values

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.783 ^a	0.613	0.608	0.626

a. Predictors: (Constant), LOY, FM-SME performance

Structural Models and Hypotheses Testing

Analysis of Direct Effects in Path Models

Figure 2(a) indicates SEM outputs without a mediator while Figure 2(b) exemplifies SEM outputs with a mediator. They highlight the magnitude and direction of relationships among constructs.

Figure 2 (a) Structural Model without Mediator

Figure 2 (b) Structural Model with Mediator

The two models exhibited good fit based on such indices as the CFI, TLI, and Relative Fit Index (RFI), TMSEA, and Chi-square/degrees of freedom ratio (χ^2/df). The CFI, TLI, and Relative Fit Index (RFI) coefficients surpassed the endorsed cut-off score of 0.90, while RMSEA values were lower than 0.08. Further evidence to support the model was provided by the Chi-square/df ratios (1.779 and 1.704). Additional indices like the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual and the Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI) were calculated to enhance the fit evaluation. The value of SRMR was 0.0508 (<0.08) and GFI was 0.888 which also show a good model fit. Taken together, these indices provide indication of model suitability in capturing the relationships among constructs.

The analysis of direct effects in path models (Table 6), examines the effect of SupO dimensions on FM-SMEs performance before and after the inclusion of a mediator (LOY). As shown in Table 6, the analysis revealed that all SupO dimensions (CRS, ISS, SES) positively and significantly influence FM-SME performance before including the mediator, suggesting that supplier-oriented practices are beneficial in direct terms. While all coefficients were statistically significant, there was varying magnitudes among SupO dimensions.

In absolute terms, CRS emerged as the soundest predictor ($\beta = 0.421, p < 0.001$), emphasizing the vital role of strategic, long-term partnerships with suppliers. CRS facilitate innovation and co-creation of value that drive superior firm performance (Stekelorum et al., 2022). In standardised terms, ISS had the most powerful significant positive effect ($\beta = 0.396, p < 0.001$), though slightly weaker than CRS in absolute terms. This highlights the importance of transparent communication for operational agility and risk mitigation. Effective ISS enables better demand forecasting, inventory management, and responsiveness to market changes, hence reducing delays and inefficiencies.

Table 6: Analysis of Direct Effects

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	Standardized Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	<i>p</i>
A: Excluding the Mediator							
FM-SME performance	<---	CRS	0.421	0.349	0.075	5.596	***
FM-SME performance	<---	ISS	0.396	0.412	0.054	7.279	***
FM-SME performance	<---	SES	0.141	0.192	0.038	3.725	***
B: Including the Mediator							
H ₆ : LOY	<---	SES	0.113	0.143	0.043	2.590	0.010
H ₅ : LOY	<---	ISS	0.328	0.317	0.059	5.597	***
H ₇ : LOY	<---	CRS	0.568	0.436	0.092	6.155	***
H ₃ : FM-SME performance	<---	CRS	0.170	0.139	0.071	2.402	0.016
H ₁ : FM-SME performance	<---	ISS	0.250	0.257	0.050	5.031	***
H ₂ : FM-SME performance	<---	SES	0.089	0.120	0.035	2.562	0.010
H ₄ : FM-SME performance	<---	LOY	0.459	0.487	0.065	7.019	***

In contrast, SES had lowest direct effect ($\beta = 0.141$, $p < 0.001$), advocating that while proper vetting of suppliers remains necessary, its transactional nature limits its ability to generate significant performance advantages on its own. While weaker than CRS and ISS, SES still plays a supportive role in firm performance by ensuring that suppliers meet quality, cost, and reliability standards. Rigorous SES may reduce defects, delivery delays, and supply chain disruptions, hence, enhancing firm performance. The initial positive and significant path coefficients without a mediator satisfies the first condition for mediation analysis before testing indirect pathways (Baron & Kenny, 1986).

After including the mediator, the path estimates for ISS, SES, and CRS decreased but remained at 5% level positive and statistically significant, establishing LOY as a significant mediator. The outputs support H₁, H₂, and H₃ and signify that LOY explains part but not all of the relationship between SupO dimensions and performance. The substantial reduction in CRS's direct effect (by 60%) when accounting for LOY suggests that much of CRS's benefit operates through building LOY. This aligns with SCIT, as CRS likely enhances performance by enabling value co-creation that customers recognize and reward with loyalty. ISS maintained a relatively stronger direct effect even after accounting for LOY (37% reduction), implying that information sharing benefits firms through multiple pathways beyond just customer retention, such as operational efficiency and innovation. SES showed the smallest mediation effect, consistent with its transactional nature having less influence on customer relationships.

While all paths were statistically significant, the emphasis should also be placed on the magnitude of effects observed. For example, although SES exhibited a statistically

significant path to firm performance, its standardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.120$) suggests a relatively modest practical impact. This contrasts with the stronger effects of CRS and ISS, reinforcing the idea that not all supplier orientation strategies yield equal operational returns. These distinctions are essential for managers seeking to prioritize limited resources.

The results further revealed that all SupO dimensions positively influenced LOY, with path estimates for ISS ($\beta = 0.328, p < 0.001$), SES ($\beta = 0.113, p < 0.05$), and CRS ($\beta = 0.568, p < 0.001$) favouring H5, H6, and H7. The results suggest that while SES contributes to loyalty, collaborative practices and information exchange matter more for building enduring customer relationships. Notably, LOY itself had a substantial direct effect on FM-SMEs performance ($\beta = 0.459, p < 0.001$), supporting H4 and confirming its role as an important mediator. The LOY's positive influence on FM-SMEs performance associates with the findings by Sampaio et al. (2020) & Ismail (2022), which established that LOY translates into higher sales, profitability, and market share.

Overall, comparisons of the models indicated that controlling for the effect of LOY reduced the path estimates for ISS, SES, and CRS; however, the estimates remained statistically significant. Thus, while LOY enhances the impact of SupO on performance, a direct effect still exists, highlighting the potential for partial mediation.

Analysis of the Mediating Effect

Prior to assessing mediation, measurement invariance across firm sizes (micro, small, and medium) was tested to ensure consistent interpretation of the model. Both configural (CMIN/DF = 1.534/1.498) and metric invariance ($\Delta\text{CMIN} = 33.915, p = 0.808$) met the required thresholds (TLI/CFI > 0.9, RMR < 0.08), confirming that the measurement invariance was achieved and hence constructs are interpreted equivalently across different firm types allowing pooled analysis. With measurement invariance confirmed, mediation analytically was performed using bootstrapping to enhance the robustness and the results' validity were obtained via CB-SEM. Tables 7, 8, and 9 present the outputs of the analysis of LOY's moderating function on the effects of ISS, SES and CRS on FP.

Table 7: Effects of ISS, SES, and CRS on LOY

A: Model Summary						
R	R-squared	MSE	F	df1	df2	<i>p</i>
0.6686	0.4470	0.5578	93.2130	3.0000	346.0000	0.0000
B: Model parameter estimates						
	Coeff.	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	0.0000	0.0399	0.0000	1.0000	-0.0785	0.0785
ISS	0.3081	0.0445	6.9273	0.0000	0.2206	0.3956
SES	0.1323	0.0460	2.8773	0.0043	0.0419	0.2227
CRS	0.3949	0.0489	8.0715	0.0000	0.2987	0.4911

The results discovered that the value of R-squared was 0.447, signifying that SES, ISS, and CRS collectively explained 45% of the variance in the LOY. Each predictor variable had a positive and statistically significant effect on LOY, as proved by their respective

confidence interval ranges in exclusion of a zero value at the 95% level. This confirms that increases in these predictor variables are associated with increases in the LOY.

In the subsequent analysis, it was found that accounting for LOY, predictor variables, and LOY explained 61% of the variance in FM-SMEs performance, as illustrated in Table 8. Each variable showed a positive and statistically significant effect on FM-SMEs' performance, with LOY showing the highest effect. This reinforces the LOY's function as a crucial driver in influencing firm performance.

Table 8: Direct Effects of ISS, SES, and CRS on FP, Accounting for LOY

A: Model Summary						
R	R-squared	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
0.7827	0.6126	0.3919	136.3789	4.0000	345.0000	0.0000
B: Model Parameter Estimates						
	Coeff.	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	0.0000	0.0335	0.0000	1.0000	-0.0658	0.0658
CRS	0.1772	0.0447	3.9631	0.0001	0.0892	0.2651
LOY	0.4105	0.0451	9.1091	0.0000	0.3218	0.4991
SES	0.1126	0.0390	2.8881	0.0041	0.0359	0.1893
ISS	0.2794	0.0398	7.0231	0.0000	0.2011	0.3576

Bootstrapping was utilised to determine the indirect effects of SES, ISS, and CRS on FM-SMEs performance via LOY. Table 9 shows the results of mediation for each predictor variable according to the bootstrap method.

Table 9: Indirect Effects of ISS, SES, and CRS on FP, Accounting for LOY

Predictors	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
CRS	0.1621	0.0292	0.1085	0.2219
ISS	0.1265	0.0236	0.0825	0.1751
SES	0.0543	0.0189	0.0192	0.0930

Note: Bootstrap resampling = 5,000 at the 95% level.

As shown in Table 9, the study revealed positive and statistically significant indirect effects for all SupO dimensions. CRS had the highest indirect effect ($\beta = 0.1621$) as it facilitates co-innovation, responsiveness, and creates value perceived by customers. ISS also had a notable significant indirect effect ($\beta = 0.1265$), suggesting that accurate and prompt communication with suppliers enhances LOY by adapting to market trends, reliability, and consistency. SES, on the other hand, had the lowest indirect effect ($\beta = 0.0543$), which indicates that its role is important but insufficient as a single strategy.

While all SupO dimensions are empirically linked to firm performance and LOY, their relative strengths vary. It can be argued that CRS and ISS are proactive, relational drivers of LOY and competitive advantage, while SES merely focuses on transactional issues such as quality, cost-effectiveness, and reliability in the selection of suppliers. SES is less directly impactful on customer-facing outcomes. Therefore, to effectively leverage supplier capabilities into enhanced LOY and superior performance, FM-SMEs should

prioritize relational strategies, such as CRS and ISS, while maintaining adequate supplier evaluation standards.

Overall Discussion and Contextual Interpretation

Overall, the analysis of direct and indirect paths highlights the significant influence of SupO dimensions on the performance of FM-SMEs via LOY. The findings affirm LOY's position as a mediator in relating SupO and firms' performance, thereby supporting H8, H9, and H10. In particular, LOY serves as a partial mediator in relating SupO dimensions and FM-SMEs' performance.

The findings align with SCIT, which posits that superior performance is driven from solid linkages with suppliers and customers. This study extends the understanding that LOY not only enhances firm performance but also bring mediation by relating SupO and firm performance. These outputs are similar to the findings of Nguyen Thi & Nguyen Thi Thu (2022) & Rajagukguk et al. (2024). Thus, embracing SupO can lead to an increased LOY, which subsequently improves firm performance.

The lowest effect of SES reflects the reality that FM-SMEs operate without formal contracts, which may limit the effectiveness of supplier evaluation practices. The observed stronger impact of CRS and ISS reflects the reality intense import competition from imported furniture, compels local enterprises to focus on building flexible relationship that offer cost efficiency and timely delivery. These findings contribute contextually relevant insights on how supply chain integration in Tanzania is shaped by informality, limited resources, and external market pressures. As such, supplier integration strategies in emerging markets must be tailored to the local context, especially where supply chains are still developing and formal systems are weak.

Conclusion, Implications and Recommendations

Conclusion

The research reveals compelling evidence that SupO is paramount for enhancing FM-SMEs' performance through LOY as a mediator. While all three dimensions of SupO contribute to firm performance, the impact is primarily through CRS and ISS. Thus, FM-SMEs that focus on building genuine partnerships with suppliers rather than transactional relationships, are greatly exposed to opportunity of creating competitiveness that resonates throughout the value chain. As the furniture industry continues to evolve, SMEs must prioritise partnership-oriented strategies to ensure resilience and competitiveness in the marketplace.

Implications of the Study

Theoretical Implication

This study takes market orientation beyond the conventional perspective by validating SupO as a crucial dimension in driving firm performance. It reinforces SCIT by empirically confirming LOY as a mediator between SupO dimensions and firm

performance, highlighting the interconnectedness of upstream and downstream strategies. The findings enrich theoretical frameworks on supply chain management and market orientation, particularly in emerging market SMEs contexts.

Practical implications for FM-SMEs

The findings offer actionable insights for FM-SMEs by establishing how different SupO practices influence performance. The strong impact of CRS suggests that investing in long-term partnerships yields greater returns than transactional approaches, particularly through enhanced innovation capabilities and LOY. The significant role of ISS highlights the value of communication with suppliers for improving agility and responsiveness. Meanwhile, the limited impact of SES indicates that while quality control remains necessary, it should not be the primary focus of supplier management strategies.

Practical implications for FM-SMEs

The study justifies a need for policy interventions aimed at enhancing support for strategic supplier partnership and fostering information sharing practices among FM-SMEs to improve their competitiveness and performance.

Recommendations

To improve performance through SupO, FM-SMEs should adopt low-cost, practical strategies. Give their financial and operational constraints, FM-SMEs can engage in informal supplier pooling arrangements, such as shared transport, bulk purchasing of raw materials, or joint negotiation of better supply terms. These forms of informal clusters can improve input reliability and reduce procurement costs without requiring significant capital.

Moreover, FM-SME can strengthen information sharing by leveraging mobile platforms like WhatsApp for real-time updates and coordination with suppliers. To improve SES, they can develop simple checklists based on delivery timeliness, material quality, and responsiveness to make evidence-based sourcing decisions without needing sophisticated procurement systems.

To nurture LOY, FM-SMEs should build a positive reputation among customers by offering superior product quality, delivering customised and memorable experiences that keep customers returning, communicating their values, and utilising modern and stylish designs.

The government, through the MIT should support FM-SMEs through training programmes focusing on building capacity in supplier management and LOY strategies to optimise their performance. The ministry should also facilitate and support the formation of SMEs cooperatives or clusters to enhance collective bargaining and reduce procurement costs.

Limitations and Areas for Further Study

The results have some limitations that require acknowledgement. First, the exclusive use of a quantitative approach limits our understanding of the underlying dynamics of SupO practices and LOY. Second, the research did not examine other important moderating variables, like enterprise size, age, or market competition, which could stimulate the strengths or directions of the relationships between SupO and firm performance. Third, the use of self-reported data from firm owners and managers makes the findings prone to social desirability and bias, particularly in responses related to performance and LOY. Fourth, while this study is based on data from Tanzanian FM-SMEs, the findings may not hold broader relevance for other countries. Future studies should incorporate qualitative approaches to offer richer insights. Additionally, future research should examine these contextual factors to uncover when and for whom SupO strategies are most effective.

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Appendix:

Description of Study Constructs with Corresponding Observable Items

Variable	Code	Measurement Items
Firm Performance (FP)	FP1	Sales have shown consistent growth over the past 5 years, meeting our expectations
	FP2	Sales growth has been on par with our competitors over the past 5 years
	FP3	We have demonstrated good ability to overcome challenges and obstacles to achieve sales growth
	FP4	Workforce has increased over the past 5 years
	FP5	Growth in number of employees has been in line with competitors over the past 5 years
	FP6	Profitability has noticeably increased over the past 5 years
	FP7	We have experienced an increase in market share over the past five years
	FP8	Our Return on Assets (ROA) has remained stable, indicating asset growth
	FP9	Our enterprise has experienced increase in asset value over the past five years
	FP10	Our enterprise has effectively utilized financial resources to expand its operations
	FP11	We have diversified our asset portfolio to maximize growth
	FP12	Our strategic initiatives have yielded significant profit growth
Supplier Evaluation and Selection	SES1	We investigate the offered assortment of different suppliers well
	SES2	We assess suppliers' ability to meet quality standards consistently
	SES3	We evaluate suppliers' delivery reliability and lead times
	SES4	We select suppliers based on their ability to meet quality standards
	SES5	We select suppliers based on their suppliers' pricing structures
	SES6	We evaluate suppliers' flexibility in accommodating changes in demand or design
Corroborative Relationships with Suppliers	CRS1	We view suppliers as strategic partners rather than just vendors
	CSR2	We participate in training programmes offered by our suppliers on new materials and technologies
	CSR3	We involve suppliers at early stage of the product development process to foster innovation
	CSR4	We work with suppliers to explore innovative opportunities and new markets

Variable	Code	Measurement Items
	CSR5	We value and act on feedback from our suppliers to strengthen our partnerships
	CSR6	We are committed to resolving conflicts with suppliers amicably
	CSR7	We consistently engage with our suppliers to address and resolve material quality concerns
Information Sharing with Suppliers	ISS1	We actively update our suppliers on changes in product designs or specifications
	ISS2	We share market trends and customer preferences with our suppliers
	ISS3	We offer suppliers with constructive feedback to help them improve their products and services
	ISS4	We proactively discuss potential supply disruptions with our suppliers and develop contingency plan
	ISS5	Our suppliers provide innovative ideas to enhance our products
Customer Loyalty (LOY)	LOY1	Our customers often return to make repeat purchases
	LOY2	We regularly receive new customers referred by existing customers
	LOY3	We regularly receive positive feedback from repeat customers
	LOY4	Our customers are more forgiving of occasional mistakes or issues
	LOY5	Our customers are willing to pay premium price for our furniture

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